

COPD and its comorbidities: Impact, measurement and mechanisms.

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Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

*"Preventable and treatable disease characterized by airflow limitation, resulting from an abnormal inflammatory reaction to inhaled particles (smoking) and **associated with co-morbidities**"*

GOLD accessed May 2018

In patients with COPD, not all Co-Morbidities are created equal

From the Solar System to the Milky Way
(Multi-morbidity)

We need to re-think how we link
diseases....perhaps by pathobiology?

Comorbidity in COPD

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Co-morbidity in COPD

COPD

Lung cancer

Chest x-ray showing a primary lung cancer

Anxiety and depression

"The pain grew and grew and I began to experience suicidal thoughts. I realized that life for me was at a desperate impasse. I thought of the garage as a place where I might sit in the car and inhale carbon monoxide. I'd look at the rafters in the attic and think of them as places where I might hang myself. I looked at sharp objects as being implements for my wrist."

9 - 20%

20-60%

30%

30-50%

17%

Cachexia

vs
myopathy

Osteoporosis

30-50%

Anemia

CAD/CHF

ATHEROSCLEROSIS

Normal Artery Mild Atherosclerosis Severe Atherosclerosis

TORCH: Causes of death as adjudicated by the Endpoint Committee

Comorbidities in patients with COPD

3100 patients

Attending P.R.

Aim: Effect of comorbidities on response to P.R.

FEV1 = 49%

Age = 71

Comorbidities and Risk of Mortality in Patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

78 comorbidities

Prevalence (%)

Comorbidities and Risk of Mortality in Patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

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Co-morbidity in COPD

Highway network

Air traffic network

Poisson

Scale-free

Figure 2. Poisson and scale-free networks. For more explanation, see text. (Courtesy of Prof. M. Perpiña, Valencia, Spain.)

New Concepts: Network Medicine

Dynamic Network Approach for the Study of Human Phenotypes

Definitions

Co-morbidity relationship exists between two diseases whenever they affect the same individual substantially more than chance alone

The COPD (Comorbidity + Clinical Characteristics) Network

- 86 Nodes
 - 79 Comorbidities
 - 7 Clinical characteristics
- 520 Connections

Divo et al (BODE COHORT)

Motif 2

Motif 3

Objectives of Study

COPD and Lung Cancer: Big Problems

One agent, two diseases.....or is it?

Pathobiological symbiosis

Facing the problem

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Top 10 Causes of Death, Years of Life Lost from Premature Death, Years Lived with Disability, and Disability-Adjusted Life-Years (DALYs) in the United States, 2010.

Table 1. Top 10 Causes of Death, Years of Life Lost from Premature Death, Years Lived with Disability, and Disability-Adjusted Life-Years (DALYs) in the United States, 2010.

Cause of Death	Deaths (N=2664)		Years of Life Lost (N=45,145)		Years Lived with Disability (N=36,689)		DALYs (N=81,835)	
	Rank	No. (%)	Rank	No. (%)	Rank	No. (%)	Rank	No. (%)
		<i>in thousands</i>		<i>in thousands</i>		<i>in thousands</i>		<i>in thousands</i>
Ischemic heart disease	1	563 (21.1)	1	7165 (15.9)	16	685 (1.9)	1	7850 (9.6)
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	5	154 (5.8)	4	1913 (4.2)	6	1745 (4.8)	2	3659 (4.5)
Low back pain	—	—	—	—	1	3181 (8.7)	3	3181 (3.9)
Cancer of the trachea, bronchus, or lung	3	163 (6.1)	2	2988 (6.6)	73	45 (0.1)	4	3033 (3.7)
Major depressive disorder	—	—	—	—	2	3049 (8.3)	5	3049 (3.7)
Other musculoskeletal disorders	36	14 (0.5)	37	254 (0.6)	3	2603 (7.1)	6	2857 (3.5)
Stroke	2	172 (6.5)	3	1945 (4.3)	17	629 (1.7)	7	2574 (3.1)
Diabetes mellitus	6	86 (3.2)	7	1392 (3.1)	8	1165 (3.2)	8	2557 (3.1)
Road-traffic injury	12	44 (1.7)	5	1873 (4.1)	26	373 (1.0)	9	2246 (2.7)
Drug-use disorders	27	19 (0.7)	15	841 (1.9)	7	1295 (3.5)	10	2136 (2.6)
Neck pain	—	—	—	—	4	2134 (5.8)	11	2134 (2.6)
Alzheimer's disease and other dementias	4	158 (5.9)	9	1192 (2.6)	12	830 (2.3)	12	2022 (2.5)
Anxiety disorders	—	—	—	—	5	1866 (5.1)	13	1866 (2.3)
Self-harm	16	37 (1.4)	6	1457 (3.2)	121	6 (<0.05)	14	1463 (1.8)
Cirrhosis of the liver	11	50 (1.9)	8	1233 (2.7)	98	16 (<0.05)	16	1249 (1.5)
Chronic kidney disease	9	60 (2.3)	16	780 (1.7)	22	410 (1.1)	17	1191 (1.5)
Colorectal cancers	8	64 (2.4)	10	1074 (2.4)	56	73 (0.2)	18	1147 (1.4)
Lower respiratory tract infections	7	85 (3.2)	11	1032 (2.3)	62	61 (0.2)	20	1093 (1.3)
Asthma	61	4 (0.2)	57	100 (0.2)	10	932 (2.5)	24	1032 (1.3)
Osteoarthritis	—	—	—	—	9	994 (2.7)	25	994 (1.2)
Other cardiovascular and circulatory diseases	10	57 (2.1)	17	765 (1.7)	34	213 (0.6)	26	979 (1.2)

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Airflow obstruction and lung Cancer

113 COPD/113 smoker without COPD

10 yrs of follow up

“The rate of development of lung cancer was significantly different in the two groups ($p = 0.024$): the 10-year cumulative percentage was 8.8% for cases and 2.0% for controls”¹

“Among cigarette smokers, the presence of airways obstruction was more of an indicator for the subsequent development of lung cancer than was age or the level of smoking”²

1. Skillrud DM. Ann Intern Med. 1986;105:503

2. Tockman MS. Ann Intern Med. 1987; 106:512

Lung Cancer in Bullous Emphysema

Assessing the relationship between lung cancer risk and emphysema detected on low-dose CT of the chest

Number = 1,666 ever-smokers. Screened for Cancer.
Spain

Odds Ratio for a diagnosis of lung cancer

	RR	IC 95%
Emphysema	2,51	1,01– 6,23
COPD	2,10	0,79 – 5,58

Adjusted for age, sex and pack-years, emphysema or COPD.

Association of Radiographic Emphysema and Airflow Obstruction with Lung Cancer

Number = 3,678 screened for lung cancer.
Pittsburgh.

	OR	95%CI
Emphysema	3.14	1.91– 5.15
COPD	1.41	0.87- 2.29

Adjusted for age, sex and smoking and emphysema or COPD

Lung Cancer in Patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

Incidence and Predicting Factors

primary group

- 2517 pts mean follow up 60 months
- 216 cases of lung cancer (8,5%)
- Incidence density 1.62/100 persons year
- Most frequent histological type: squamous cell
- 914 died during the follow up time
- 134 due to lung cancer

Lung Cancer in Patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

Incidence and Predicting Factors

Predictors of Lung Cancer development

Parameter	Hazard Ratio	95% Confidence Interval	P Value
Age	1.02	1.00–1.04	0.02
BMI	0.95	0.92–0.99	0.01
GOLD stage			
I	3.05	1.41–6.59	0.005
II	2.06	1.01–4.18	0.04
III	1.67	0.81–3.44	0.16
IV	Reference		
DL _{CO} <80% predicted	1.76	1.15–2.69	0.009

Synerg
Conver
e

Lung
Cancer

COPD

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Common Variants, Low Penetrance

GWAS in lung cancer with COPD phenotype considered:

SNP in Genes	Phenotype
<i>CHRNA3/5</i>	Lung cancer + COPD
<i>FAM13A</i>	Lung cancer + COPD
<i>BAT3</i>	Lung cancer + COPD
<i>TERT</i>	Lung cancer
<i>HHIP</i>	Lung cancer + COPD
<i>ADAM19</i>	Lung cancer + COPD
<i>AGER</i>	COPD
<i>CRP</i>	Lung cancer

(Young, PLoS ONE, 2011)

State of the Art

Oxidative stress

Cell replication and senescence

Gene expression

Epigenetics
Methylation

Endogenous modifiers

Co-morbidities

Microbiota

Pathobiological Symbiosis

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A Road to the Future

Some co-morbidities of COPD share pathobiological responses to injurious agents and occur more frequently than chance would have it.

We may have to shift from organ oriented pathophysiology to mechanistic pathobiology

Comprehensive evaluation of patients for commonly occurring diseases

Merging of specialties? Back to Holistic Medicine